

Service Ecosystem for Project Management and Innovation in Ivano-Frankivsk Region

Concept Paper / Technical Specification (Preprint Version 1.0 — 2025)

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- NGO “Agenty Zmin IF”
- Regional development institutions (IFR Strategy 2025–2027 partners)

Abstract

This preprint presents the concept of the regional development initiative **“Service Ecosystem for Project Management and Innovation in Ivano-Frankivsk Region.”** The project aims to increase the region’s investment potential and strengthen its innovation infrastructure by establishing a unified service ecosystem that integrates analytical, advisory, educational, and expert-support functions.

The paper addresses systemic challenges hindering regional competitiveness: low investment activity, insufficient innovation capacity, limited platforms for investor engagement, and the absence of structured analytical tools for communities. The project foresees creation of ten analytical investor reviews, ten EU-standard community investment passports, ten investment project concept notes, and the operational launch of the service ecosystem as a regional project-management hub.

Expected outcomes include strengthened institutional capacity, improved investment attractiveness, and enhanced cooperation with international organizations and development funds. By 2027, the ecosystem is projected to facilitate attracting at least **15 million UAH** in investments and grants.

Keywords

Investment potential; Innovation infrastructure; Project management ecosystem; Regional development; Investment promotion; EU standards; Analytical products; CNU.

1. Project Title

Service Ecosystem for Project Management and Innovation in Ivano-Frankivsk Region

2. Submitters

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4. Alignment with Regional Strategy 2025–2027

The project corresponds to the following objectives within the **Ivano-Frankivsk Regional Development Strategy 2021–2027**:

- **1.2.4.** Effective cooperation between government, business, and science
- **1.2.5.** Enhancing investment attractiveness and investment promotion
- **1.2.8.** Support for regional innovation systems (science parks, technoparks, DIHs)
- **1.3.2.** Conditions for industrial investment and cluster development
- **3.1.1.** Updating strategic planning documents to support sustainable recovery

5. Target Territory

Ivano-Frankivsk region, with emphasis on underdeveloped communities with high investment potential.

6. Problem Statement

The regional innovation infrastructure remains fragmented and ineffective.

Key challenges include:

- low investment activity,
- weak promotion of regional opportunities,
- insufficient analytical and project-design tools,
- lack of coordinated platforms for investor engagement,
- limited institutional capacity to support innovation processes.

These findings are supported by regional analytical reviews (<http://surl.li/avimrf>).

7. Expected Quantitative Results

- Establishment of the **Service Ecosystem for Project Management and Innovation**
- **10 analytical investor reviews**
- **10 EU-standard investment passports** for communities
- **10 investment project concept notes**
- Attraction of **15+ million UAH** in investments and grants by 2027

8. Expected Qualitative Results

- Enhanced investment attractiveness of the region
- Stronger institutional capacity of innovation infrastructure
- Improved cooperation with international development funds and partners

9. Key Project Indicators

Indicator	Value
Analytical reviews	10
Investment passports	10
Concept notes	10

Indicator	Value
Updated/new infrastructure institutions	3
Investment volume attracted	≥ 15 million UAH

10. Main Project Activities

1. Establishment and launch of the Service Ecosystem
2. Training and facilitation sessions for local authorities, civil society, and business
3. Preparation of the project concept note portfolio
4. Involvement of international experts for investment potential assessment
5. Promotion of investment and innovation opportunities through international partnerships

11. Budget Overview (2025–2027)

Funding Source	2025	2026	2027	Total
Regional Budget	4000.0	4000.0	4000.0	12000.0
Other local budgets	—	—	—	—
Other sources (regional program, donors)	180.0	180.0	180.0	540.0
Total Funding	4180.0	4180.0	4180.0	12540.0

12. Additional Information

The project will be implemented by the **Agents of Changes Centre, CNU**, using advanced digital tools and AI-based project development models (<http://surl.li/atfide>).

Implementation will involve collaboration with regional departments, local authorities, development institutions, associations, and international partners.

The initiative aligns with the **Integrated Regional Program for University Engagement 2024–2027**, approved by the Ivano-Frankivsk Regional Council (Decision №951-33/2024).

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